

Interview Musée Maritime de Nouvelle - Calédonie – Marie Arnautou
19.05, 5.07 and 09.07.2021 / 6h

Name: Michaela Florescu
Updated: 2021-07-28

WP2. Investigating the conservation of WWII wrecks (land or underwater), and more particularly parts made of Al alloys.

- Presentation of the institution :

The Musée Maritime de Nouvelle-Calédonie focuses on the maritime history of New Caledonia, and in particular the voyages of La Pérouse (1785-1788).

90% of the marine archaeological items displayed in the museum were collected by members of the "Association Fortunes de Mer Calédoniennes" and "Association Salomon", on a large number of historical wrecks.

The Museum's collections include over 8000 items. About half of the items in the Museum's collections were collected from the two vessels of the La Pérouse expedition, wrecked in 1788 at Vanikoro Island, Solomon Islands. The rest of the items on display come from wrecks discovered around the New Caledonian reefs.

The Museum collections also include items relating to maritime activities: lighthouse equipment, lights and buoys, charts, ship models, navigation instruments. Some of these items (10%) are on loan to the Museum from private collections.

(source : <https://museemaritime.nc/english/>)

- The operating chain: from the wreck to the museum

At what stage or stages of the operating chain has (or is) the institution/ group / association been involved ? Defining a recovery project? Integrating wrecks or artefacts from wrecks in the collection? Do they have direct input in defining the projects or just executing ? What is their approach? Is it similar or different approach if different projects ?

Most of the items in the collections have been recovered by the association Fortunes de Mer Calédoniennes.

The association exists for 30 years, they decide what wrecks are to be explored and what objects/elements are to be brought back ashore. The association takes care of the archive and documentary research preliminary to the exploration of the wreck. They also request authorizations required for recovery.

The association always gives their finds to the museum. The museum is not involved in the selection of objects to be brought back but has responsibility of the management of items from the wrecks after recovery. The museum accepts all objects given to them; there is no selection, even if the objects are not considered very interesting or if the recovery is not documented.

In the last few years, there is approximately 1 recovery campaign per year, approximately 10 objects are brought each time. Earlier campaigns were more numerous and concerned more items.

Relationships between the museum and the association are quite tensed, communication is rather difficult.

New-Caledonia has a specific legal status, does not depend of DRASSM. All the sunken wrecks belong to the provinces of New-Caledonia, except the national wrecks who belong to the French state, and therefore fall under DRASSM regulations. Association's members are now mainly retirees, a little withdrawn within themselves

Museum is in the Southern Province, but the collections include objects recovered in waters belonging to the North Province. There haven't been any questions about ownership of the objects so far, but Marie has no clear information about the official procedure to follow.

- Concept of "conservation": Do you think of long-term preservation/conservation of the artefacts you handle? How do you define long term? What does the idea of "conservation" mean to you for this kind of heritage ? How would you want that heritage to be passed on to future generations ? Has that definition shifted over time for you/the institution ?

Recoveries by the association are rather random. There is no defined strategy, to evaluate interest or value of what is brought back. The association has more of a treasure hunter's approach.

The museum carries out treatments as a basic obligation to ensure the conservation of their collections. No strategy for choosing the preserved objects. Process is depending on what the association does, the museum is not involved in the excavations, does not have the choice to refuse the association's contributions or to select what is brought back.

- Who works on these collections (after recovery) : conservators, technical staff (aviation background or not), volunteers? What training for these different stakeholders? Do they work in collaboration? Are they internal or external to the museum? What is the relationship between museum management / conservation and the people in charge of interventions directly ? (addition to Form A)

Diving and recovery of the objects, as well as immediate actions like cleaning are entirely carried out by the association. The association also ensure transportation and storage of the objects until they are handed over to the museum.

Conservation is carried out by Marie Arnautou, a trained conservator, graduated from HE-ARC (Switzerland). She joined the museum 6 years ago. Her predecessor was not a trained conservator.

- Conditions of conservation of the collection / artefact : aircraft in working order with regular maintenance / complete planes (or nearly) with or without preventive conservation / wrecks or elements of wrecks: exposed or not, kept in storage /outdoors (addition to Form A) ?

No complete aircraft. Only parts or artefacts from aircrafts, such as : fragments, on-board instruments, cockpit plates, viewfinder, machine gun.

Not all artefacts are on display, some artefacts in storage at the museum. No artefacts are outdoors. The museum has closed storage but not watertight; the artefacts are kept on open shelves, with a little dust protection with plastic sheet. Climate and light not controlled.

During temporary storage by the association, artefacts are kept by the members, at home or in their personal storage spaces (uncontrolled environment).

- Conditions of storage location (exhibition room or storage) : rooms or hall ? awareness about influence of climate on preservation? Monitoring or not of RH & T ° and their changes during the year (addition to Form A) ?

The museum is located in a former maritime terminal in the Nouméa Port.

The museum's building is an old converted industrial building, not optimal for implementing climate control. The storage has no controlled environment.

In the exhibition spaces there are sensors for measuring RH and T° (4 mobile data loggers). RH variations can go up to 40%, T° variations can go up to 15°C.

A nickel treatment factory is located nearby.

- Reflecting on their own practice : do you feel that you know everything you would like to when it comes to managing this sort of artefacts ? What would be the aspects you would like to know more about ? Do you keep informed or in contact with other stakeholders in this field ? Has your practice evolved through those connections?

There is little room for changing the relationship with the association and any procedure regarding the recovery and reception of the objects from the association.

Treatment protocols have moved towards conservation since Marie Arnautou arrived at the museum.

The museum is interested in acquiring more knowledge about aluminum alloys, their degradations, and possible treatments. They are also interested in advice for better practice in the operational chain and post-recovery actions.

- Conservation problem that may be encountered with Al alloys (questions and needs if there are any, or practices for solving these problems) ? Does it feel like a priority concern regarding your corpus of WWII wrecks ? regarding the rest of the collection (if relevant)? What type of treatment protocols are (or have been) carried out (addition to Form A)?

Corrosion of Fe and Al alloys seems to be equally worrying.

Corrosion types observed on Al alloy :

- surface white powdery and non-adherent corrosion products (early stage) and hardened and bulky with beginning of crater underneath (advanced stage)

- bluish powdery (with crater underneath) and crusty corrosion products (with metal brittle underneath).
- the bluish crusts can be a calcareous deposits mixed with corrosion products.
- Fe elements stained the Al sheets

Treatments:

In the past, treatments were mainly removal of calcareous concretions with HCl and mechanical treatment.

The current protocols involve rinsing the object when it arrives, usually in a bath. Sometimes chemical stabilization with measurement of chlorides. But sometimes rinsing can be a little more empirical depending on the condition of the object, not always measurements.

- Promotion of WWII aeronautical heritage, influence of the country's history in the conflict and the relationship to that history ?

New-Caledonia was a neutral territory during WWII, but it became a fallback base for US army after Pearl Harbor in 1942. There are many American WWII wrecks in the area.

The museum is not focused on WWII period. WWII wrecks are integration in one the main sections of the permanent exhibition, called "American presence".

There are 15 known WWII wrecks in nearby waters (2 seaplanes, the rest are aircrafts), 5 have been explored so far.